

EFFECT OF YOGIC PRACTICES ON STRESS LEVEL AMONG ADVOCATES

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Abstract:

The purpose of the present study was to find out the effect of yogic practices on stress among male advocates. Only twenty male advocates doing practice in the judicial magistrate court at Thiruthani within the jurisdiction of Thiruvallur district, Tamil Nadu state in India are randomly selected as subjects their age ranges from 40 to 50 years. The subjects are divided into two equal groups in which each group consisted of ten subjects. Group-I underwent yoga training for eight weeks, 60 minutes daily for six days per week. Group-II (Control group) was not exposed to any training/conditioning other than their daily routines activities. Only pre and post tests were taken. Random group design was used. Group allotment such as experimental and control group are also made randomly. John D & Catherine T. Mac Arthur questionnaire was used to measure the stress level of male advocates before and after the yoga training. Analysis of covariance (ANACOVA) was applied to find out significant difference, if any between the experimental and control group as a result of eight weeks of yoga practice. In all the cases statistical significance was fixed at 0.05 levels. The result of the study revealed that due to the effect of yoga training the stress level of male advocates was significantly decreased.

Key Words: Yoga Practices & Stress

Introduction:

Yoga is an ancient art based on a harmonizing system of development for the body, mind and spirit. It is a practical aid not a religion. Stress referred to people reactions to situation in which they feel threatened pressured frustrated, anxious or in conflict pleasant and unpleasant situations can be stressful. The practice of yoga for fitness and wellness in gyms, community centres, and yoga studios is broadening into yoga therapy being provided in schools, hospitals, and community treatment centers. In fact, the leading yoga magazine, *Yoga Journal*, recently claimed that "yoga as medicine represents the next great wave". "For lawyers who want to improve their state of mind, feel healthier, be more effective, and experience better work-life balance, so Yoga for Lawyers is recommended." Lawyers deal with other people's problems and conflicts. Their jobs, and their bodies, are sedentary. Overwork causes body and mind to become disconnected and out of balance". (Hallie N and Nathalie D (2014) "Yoga class is as important as research on Westlaw. The experiences have helped to cultivate empathy and helps her identify emotions that her clients are experiencing but can't always articulate. Yoga makes her more effective with clients and judges and everyone I encounter." (Holle ST, 2013) Yogic practices, physical exercises and combination of both the trainings improve the physiological variables like blood pressure, resting pulse rate, cardio respiratory endurance and breath holding time and give positive improvement in psychological variables as anxiety, aggression, achievement motivation and self confidence. (Padmadevi, 2007).

Statement of the Problem:

The purpose of the present study was to find out the effect of yogic practices on stress among male advocates.

Objective of the Study:

The intention of the researcher is to give male advocates lifelong skills to deal with the stress of the job. The study will insist the importance of yogic practices to relieve stress.

Need and Importance of the Study:

With the rapid advancement of technology, the stresses faced at work have also increased. Many people dread going to work, hence the term "Monday Blues". What is the reason for this? There is partly the fear from seeing retrenched in bad times, leading to greater job insecurity on the part of those who remain. Undoubtedly, occupational stress is one of the most commonly cited stressors faced by people all over the world. So the researchers concentrate on this topic and selected advocates as subject for this research.

Subjects and Variables:

Only twenty male advocates doing practice in the judicial magistrate court at Thiruthani within the jurisdiction of Thiruvallur district, Tamil Nadu state in India are randomly selected as subjects their age ranges from 40 to 50 years.

Methodology:

The subjects are divided into two equal groups in which each group consisted of ten subjects. Group-I underwent yoga training for eight weeks, 60 minutes daily for six days per week. Group-II (Control group) was not exposed to any training/conditioning other than their daily routines activities. Only pre and post tests were

taken. Random group design was used. Group allotment such as experimental and control group are also made randomly. John D & Catherine T. Mac Arthur questionnaire was used to measure the stress level of male advocates before and after the yoga training.

Training Programme:

The training programmes were scheduled for one session a day, each session lasted between one hour approximately including preparation and relaxation. During the training period, the experimental groups underwent for yoga training six days a week for eight weeks. The subjects are divided into two equal groups in which each group consisted of ten subjects. Group I underwent yoga training for eight weeks, 60 minutes daily for six days per week. Group II (Control group) was not exposed to any training/conditioning other than their daily routines activities.

Table 1: Yoga Training Schedule

List of Yogasanas	Week	Maintainin g duration	Recover y	Repetition	Frequency	Preparation and Relaxation
Preparatory Practices	1-8 weeks	30 sec		1	Monday to Saturday	5 min.
suryanamaskar		5 min		4		
Virkeshasana		30 sec	1:1 ratio	2		
Trikonasana		30 sec	1:1 ratio			
Ustrasana		30 sec	1:1 ratio			
Paschimottanasana		30 sec	1:1 ratio			
Chakarasana		30 sec	1:1 ratio			
Bhujangasana		30 sec	1:1 ratio			
Shalabhasana		30 sec	1:1 ratio			
Dhanurasana		30 sec	1:1 ratio			
Halasana		30 sec	1:1 ratio			
Pranayama		5 min				
Meditation		4 min		1		
Shavasana		2 min		1		

Statistical Technique:

In this study yoga training was selected independent variable and stress was selected as dependent variable. Analysis of covariance (ANACOVA) was applied to find out significant difference, if any between the experimental and control group as a result of eight weeks of yoga practice. Statistical significance was fixed at 0.05 levels.

Analysis and Interpretation:

The influence of yoga training on stress was statistically analyzed and the results are presented below.

Table 2: Descriptive Analysis of the Pre and Post Test Data and ‘t’ Ratio on Stress of Experimental and Control Groups

Group	Test	Mean	Standard Deviation	Range	Mean Differences	‘t’ ratio
Experime ntal group	Pre test	37.70	3.71	11	4.90	21.00
	Post test	32.80	3.91	11		
Control Group	Pre test	35.90	4.20	14	0.60	0.66
	Post test	36.50	4.03	13		

Table t-ratio at 0.05 level of confidence for 9 (df) = 1.83

*Significant

Table 2 shows that the mean, standard deviation, range and mean difference values of the pre and post test data collected from the experimental and control groups on stress. Further, the collected data was statistically analyzed by paired ‘t’ test to find out the significant differences if any between the pre and post data. The obtained ‘t’ values on stress of experimental group is 21.00 which is greater than the required table value of 1.83 for significance at 0.05 level for 9 degrees of freedom. It revealed that significant differences exist between the pre and post test means of experimental group on stress. However, no significant differences exist between the pre and post test means of control group on stress, since the obtained ‘t’ value 0.66 is lesser than the required table value of 1.83 for significance at 0.05 level for 9 degrees of freedom.

The pre and post test data collected from the experimental and control groups on aggression is statistically analyzed by using analysis of covariance and the results are presented in table 3.

Table 3: Analysis of Covariance on Stress of Experimental and Control Groups

	Yoga Training Group	Control Group	SoV	Sum of Squares	df	Mean squares	‘F’ ratio
Pre test Mean	37.70	35.90	B	16.20	1	16.20	1.03

SD	3.71	4.20	W	283.00	18	15.72	
Post test Mean	32.80	36.50	B	68.45	1	68.45	4.34*
SD	3.91	4.03	W	284.10	18	15.78	
Adjusted Post test Mean	32.02	37.28	B	130.42	1	130.42	30.00
			W	73.90	17	4.35	*

Table F-ratio at 0.05 level of confidence for df 1 and 18 = 4.39, 1 and 17 = 4.45

*Significant

Table 3 shows that the pre-test means and standard deviation on stress of yoga training and control groups are 37.70 ± 3.71 and 35.90 ± 4.20 respectively. The obtained 'F' value 1.03 of stress was lesser than the required table value of 4.39 with 1, 18 df at 0.05 level of confidence.

The post-test means and standard deviation on stress of yoga training and control groups are 32.80 ± 3.91 and 36.50 ± 4.03 respectively. The obtained 'F' value of 4.34 on of yoga training was greater than the required table value of 4.39 with 1, 18 df at 0.05 level of confidence. It implied that no significant differences exist between the two groups during the post test on stress.

The adjusted post-test means on stress of yoga training and control groups were 32.02 and 37.28 respectively. The obtained 'F' value of 30.00 on stress was greater than the required table value of 4.45 of 1, 17 df at 0.05 level of confidence. Hence, it was concluded that significant differences exist between the adjusted post test means of yoga training and control groups on stress.

The pre, post and adjusted post test mean values of experimental and a control group on stress is graphically represented in figure 1.

Figure 1: Diagram Showing the Mean Values on Stress of Experimental and Control Groups

Discussion on Finding:

The result of the study revealed that due to the effect of yoga training the stress of the male advocates was significantly decreased. Performance stress comes from social evaluation and the feeling of threat to one's ego that evaluation brings. Signs of negative stress having low self confidence, making negative comments about yourself, being more self-critical, consistently performing under our ability (*particularly in pressure situations*), having trouble sleeping the night before an event, experiencing difficulty getting loose before a competition, and feeling ill or upset before an event. To change an individual's reaction to pressure requires making changes in two main categories: 1) thoughts, feelings, and perceptions of stressful situations, and 2) the physical bodily responses to stressful conditions" (Performance Media, 2006). Stress and coping are ways the body reacts and adapts to stressors to return to a state of equilibrium after a traumatic event. In order for a stress management technique to be used properly, the athlete's environment, personality, and ability to effectively use the technique need to be taken into account. Through implementing stress management techniques or reinforcing lifestyle buffers, the athlete learns to share control of the rehabilitation process with the athletic trainer (Hedgepath & Sowa, 1998).

Conclusion:

Based on the result obtained from the statistical analysis of the data the following conclusion has been derived. The result of the study revealed that due to the effect of yoga training the stress of the male advocates was significantly decreased.

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